

DEMOUNTABLE REUSABLE AND ADJUSTABLE MOMENT-RESISTING JOINTS FOR CIRCULAR CONSTRUCTION

Filip LJUBINKOVIĆ^a, Jorge C. CONDE^b, Neda JANKOVIĆ and Luís S. DA SILVA^a

^a University of Coimbra, ISISE, ARISE, Department of Civil Engineering, Portugal
E-mails: filj@uc.pt, neda.jankovic@uc.pt, luisss@dec.uc.pt

^b Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Departamento de Física y Estructuras de Edificación, Madrid, Spain
E-mail: jorge.conde@upm.es

Keywords

Circular construction;
Steel structures;
Moment-resisting joints;
Reusability;
Structural adaptability;
High strength steel.

Abstract

This paper discusses an innovative double-sided moment-resisting beam-to-beam joint, designed for the European research project Connect4C, which aims to foster the circular economy in construction through standardized, adaptable, and reusable 3D connection solutions. The proposed joint enhances structural flexibility by enabling wider spans with fewer columns and is fully demountable, addressing key aspects like adaptability and reusability. It incorporates advanced features such as long bolts and hyper-packs to facilitate horizontal adaptability and accommodate geometrical mismatches, essential for the effective reuse of beams. A numerical assessment using Abaqus software evaluates the joint under various conditions, focusing on its moment-rotation characteristics, plastic strain evolution, and potential failure modes. The study examines four models with variations in bolt preload and hyper-pack material, revealing that while high-strength steel (HSS) increases moment capacity, it also raises concerns about brittle failure under high preload scenarios. Initial results underscore the need for further optimization through a comprehensive parametric study, which will explore additional factors such as material properties, bolt preload levels, and structural geometries to enhance the joint's performance and reliability.

1 INTRODUCTION

The construction industry is a significant source of global CO₂ emissions, with a reported contribution of 39% according to the 2018 United Nations Environment Programme [1]. Efforts to mitigate these emissions focus on transitioning to a circular economy, a movement particularly relevant in construction. This transition includes designing demountable structures, optimizing material choice from the outset, and promoting the reuse of construction materials such as steel, which is highly durable and recyclable. Despite these advantages, the reuse of steel is challenged by factors like scarce material availability, the environmental cost of demolition, and the lack of standardized reuse protocols [2].

The connections between components are key to the reuse of steel structures, which account for 50% of the construction costs and are crucial for disassembly and reassembly. High-performance demountable connections, especially bolted over welded, facilitate the reuse of steel beams and columns [3]. Notable projects advancing these ideas include REDUCE [4] and INNO3DJOINTS [5], which have developed demountable connection systems

for steel construction. Although these projects demonstrate the environmental benefits of such innovations, their scope is limited to specific joint configurations, excluding moment-resisting joints and 3D joint behavior analysis.

Figure 1: Conceptual sketch of the CONNECT4C structural system and reusable joints [6]

These limitations have led to a new European research project CONNECT4C [6], initiated in 2023, focusing on developing standardized, adaptable, and reusable 3D connection solutions that leverage advanced steel grades. The project targets three main types of joints in building structures: (1) beam-to-column simple joints, (2) beam-to-column moment-resisting joints, and (3) column splices. Figure 1 shows an example of a structural system in which the CONNECT4C joints allow for reuse and easy demountability (the solutions shown are only conceptual and their final definition will be investigated during the project).

Moment-resisting (MR) joints enhance design flexibility by enabling wider spans and fewer columns, thus facilitating open floor plans and increasing architectural versatility. More effective than simple (pinned) joints, MR joints bolster a building's structural rigidity and stability by managing lateral loads, and they offer ductile behavior and large rotational capacity, improving structural redundancy. For effective reuse, MR joints need to be both demountable and adjustable, accommodating geometrical mismatches (up to about 250 mm) between reused beams and their new positions. While the REDUCE project has focused on adjustable systems for pinned connections, this paper presents a preliminary study of an MR beam-to-beam joint, exploring its development and initial findings.

2 CASE STUDY

2.1 Reference buildings

To guide the development of the CONNECT4C system (C4C system), two multi-story office buildings are selected as representatives of current market solutions. The two buildings are similar in overall dimensions and use; however, one is designed with pinned beam-to-column connections, and the second with moment-resisting. They are first designed considering standard bolted connection solutions, and subsequently, they will be redesigned to incorporate the structural characteristics of a demountable and adaptable C4C joint system, once fully developed.

The reference buildings are inspired by the real concrete office building built in Porto (Portugal) in 2020, slightly adapted to the steel and composite construction. The reference building is a 6-floor multi-story structure, with a total height of 27.85 m above the basements, with a typical floor height of 4.00 m. The overall dimensions of the building are $28.35 \times 16.20 \text{ m}^2$ (measured between column axes), as shown in Figure 2. From a structural point of view, the building is composed of a reinforced concrete core with an area of $6.75 \times 5.40 \text{ m}^2$; column steel sections above ground level; reinforced concrete solid slabs in basements and within the core and composite floors and beams in floors above ground.

The design of structural elements is carried out by the relevant Eurocodes [7]. For the solution with the moment-

resisting joints, relevant to the present paper, the main composite beams have IPE300 steel sections and are continuous across spans of 10.80, 6.75, and 10.80 m. Collecting beams along axes 'B' and 'C' utilize IPE330 profiles with spans of 5.40 m. Between axes '2' and '3', composite beams have single spans of 10.80 m and IPE360 steel sections. Using the same IPE360 steel section, collecting beams of the axis 'A' and 'D' have two continuous spans, each measuring 8.10 m. Connections between steel columns or composite beams and concrete supporting elements are considered pinned (indicated by blue circles in Figure 2). The remaining connections are modeled and designed considering the corresponding rotational stiffness (indicated by red squares in Figure 2). Composite floors are supported every 2.70 meters and have a total height of 150 mm, with 90 mm of concrete above a 60 mm profiled steel decking with a thickness of 1 mm.

Figure 2: Reference building plan

2.2 C4C system requirements

The CONNECT4C project develops a system aligned with the circular economy, emphasizing three key requirements: (1) **Adaptability**, enabling adjustments for small geometrical mismatches (up to about 250 mm) between connecting members and the structural grid; (2) **Reusability**, ensuring steel members can be easily reused and focusing on limiting deformations like hole ovalization that are not recoverable; (3) **Demountability**, facilitating easy disassembly of joints to recover undamaged structural components, with an emphasis on minimizing or eliminating welds in favor of bolted connections.

3 MOMENT RESISTING JOINTS

3.1 Joint definition

In this section, an innovative demountable double-sided beam-to-beam moment-resisting joint for open sections is developed and validated. The joint is presented in Figure 4. The joint configuration is defined based on (i) profiles used in the reference case building (IPE300 for joists and IPE330 for the collecting 'main' beam), and (ii)

C4C system requirements described in 2.2. This joint ensures continuity between the two connected members by transferring the internal forces at their interface while allowing for a possible change of cross-section dimensions. To allow for adaptability and demountability, the connection between joists and the main beam is achieved through (1) specifically designed packing elements, called “hyper-pack” (see Figure 5); (2) 18 preloaded conventional bolts (M16...10.9) between hyper-pack and joist flanges and webs as well as main beam web; and (3) two long bolts (M24...10.9) placed in the tensile zone connecting two hyper-packs, while passing through a slotted hole in the main beam.

Figure 4: Moment-resisting beam-to-beam joint

Figure 5: Hyper-pack

Given that no additional welding is applied, the joint is completely demountable. The adaptability is achieved by prefabricated hyper-pack, whose purpose is to enable joists of different lengths to be connected effectively to the main beam. It consists of five welded plates, 4 of which are 10 mm thick, while the one supporting the long bolt is 20 mm. Many bolt holes are provided with the equidistance of 50 mm, enabling different joist positions in the longitudinal direction hence adapting to various spans. To allow free access to all parts of the connection, the hyper-pack is not a closed box.

While the shear force is transferred to the main beam by 4 conventional bolts on the main beam web, the bending moment is transferred by 2 long bolts subject to pure tension, which may elongate and hence ensure a significant rotational capacity of the joint. The moment capacity M of the joint hence depends on the tensile resistance of the long bolts N_T (which is a function of its cross-section area A_b and material properties f_{tb}), as well as on the lever arm, i.e. the distance between the long bolts and the compression center of the connection (i.e. midplane of the hyper-pack bottom flange).

3.2 Numerical model

To assess the behavior of this joint, Abaqus software is used. The main beam is completely fixed, while in the free ends of the joists, only the out-of-plane movements are prevented. The external load is applied in the form of the displacements at the joist’s free ends. All the bolts, conventional and long, are class 10.9, with the bilinear material model. All plate elements are made of carbon steel S355, except for the hyper-pack, where 2 alternatives are compared (S355 and S690) to evaluate the benefit of HSS. The quad-linear material model with strain hardening is used, as per prEN 1993-1-14 [8]. In this paper, 4 models are studied, where two levels of the long bolt preload are varied (15% and 70%, corresponding to 50 kN and 230 kN, respectively), and two materials for the hyper-packs (S355 and S690). The model is discretized by solid C3D8R finite elements, whose density is adopted based on a mesh convergence study

3.3 Results

To assess the behavior of the joint, the following results are monitored and assessed for each FEM model: (1) failure mode; (2) moment-rotation curve; (3) plastic strains evolution; and (4) presence of a slip in the connection. Moment-rotation curves are obtained in a simplified way - rotation is read at the free end of a joist, and the moment is calculated as force read at the same point multiplied by the lever arm (distance between the free end of a joist and the center of the web of the main beam). An example is shown in Figure 6, where the results for the reference Model 1 (S355, 15% preload) are shown.

Figure 6: Results for Model 1 (S355, 15% preload)

Marks in this diagram indicate relevant increments in which plastic strain in the long bolt, hyper-pack, and main beam web occurs (first three marks) or reaches a 5% threshold value per prEN1993-1-14 [8] (latter three marks). In Model 1, a certain plastification occurs in all parts of the connection, however, the loss of moment capacity comes from the bending of the hyper-pack end plate that is connected to the long bolt.

The results of the other three models are assessed in the same way and compared with Model 1. To avoid the

damage in hyper-pack, in Model 2, the material of the hyper-pack is enhanced from S355 to S690, while the same level of snug-tight preload is kept. The joint initial stiffness is not affected by the change in the material; however, moment capacity is increased by 25%, from 110 kNm to 138 kNm, which matches the value obtained by hand calculations. The material change caused the shift in the failure mode from a ductile bending of the end plate in Model 1 to a brittle failure of the long bolts in Model 2, as shown in Figure 7. Therefore, additional measures need to be envisaged and studied to improve its behavior and increase system robustness.

Figure 7: Results for Model 2 (S690, 15% preload) vs Model 1

In Models 3 and 4, with the S355 and S690 hyper-pack, and an increased long bolt preload of 70%, significant plastic strain is noticed in the hyper-pack even during the preload step, therefore these models are disregarded from the study.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents and evaluates an innovative double-sided moment-resisting beam-to-beam joint designed for the Connect4C project. The joint is fully demountable and features exceptional horizontal adaptability through the use of long bolts and hyper-packs, also exploring the benefits of high-strength steel. To ensure reusability, the design prevents plastification that could lead to damage. In this preliminary study, four models are analyzed, varying the preload level of the long bolts and the material of the hyper-packs. Findings indicate that the joint layout cannot withstand high preload levels and that while high-strength steel enhances the joint's moment capacity, it also introduces a risk of brittle failure in the bolts. A parametric study is currently underway to optimize the joint configuration by examining variables such as bolt preload, hyper-pack material and thickness, and different stiffener arrangements within the hyper-pack.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was partly financed by FCT / MCTES through national funds (PIDDAC) under the R&D Unit Institute for Sustainability and Innovation in Structural Engineering (ISISE), under reference UIDB / 04029/2020 (doi.org/10.54499/UIDB/04029/2020), and under the Associate Laboratory Advanced Production and Intelligent Systems ARISE under reference LA/P/0112/2020. Grant with reference UP2021–035 (RD 289/2021) from “Ministerio de Universidades de España”, funded by European Union, NextGenerationEU, attributed to Jorge Conde. Finally, funding from the European Commission's Research Fund for Coal and Steel through the research project CONNECT4C (Grant 101112300) is highly acknowledged. Disclaimer: “Work is funded by Europe Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

REFERENCES

- [1] "Global Status Report 2018: towards a zero-emission, efficient and resilient buildings and construction sector", International Energy Agency and the United Nations Environment Programme, 2018.
- [2] Kanyilmaz, A., Birhane, M., and Fishwick, R., “Reuse of Steel in the Construction Industry: Challenges and Opportunities”, *Int J Steel Struct*, 23, 1399–1416, 2023.
- [3] Dams B., Maskell D., Shea A., Allen S., Driesser M., Kretschmann T., Walker P., and Emmitt S. “A circular construction evaluation framework to promote designing for disassembly and adaptability”, *J. Clean. Prod*, 316, 128122, 2021.
- [4] Odenbreit C., Yang J., Romero A., and Kozma A., “A reusable structural system fit for geometrical standardization and serial production”, *ce/papers* 5, 2, 2022.
- [5] Silva L.C., Tankova T., Craveiro H., Simões R., Costa R., and Simões da Silva L., “Behaviour of plug-and-play joints between RHS columns and CFS trusses”, *Structures*, 41, 1719-1745, 2022.
- [6] CONNECT4C, High-strength steel connections for circular construction. Fund for Coal and Steel, Grant Agreement No. RFCS-101112300, 2023-2027.
- [7] CEN, EN 1990:2002 - Eurocode 0: Basis of Structural Design, European Committee for Standardization, Belgium, 2002.
- [8] CEN, prEN 1993-1-14: Design of steel structures - Part 1-14: Design assisted by finite element analysis, European Committee for Standardization. Belgium, 2022.